

Organizational Silence as a Reaction to Organizational Mobbing A Study on Nurses in Egypt

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Abstract

The objective of the research is to examine Organizational Silence (OS) as a reaction to Organizational Mobbing (OM) of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt. The research population consists of all nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt. Due to time and cost constraints, the researcher adopted a sampling method to collect data for the study. The appropriate statistical methods were used to analyze the data and test the hypotheses.

The research has reached a number of results, the most important of which are: (1) despite the availability of numerous regulatory studies on variables of OM and OS, the researchers did not try to examine the relationship between them. Therefore, the aim of the present study is to bridge this research gap. Therefore, the study focused on analyzing the relationship between OM and OS. Hence, the current study is one of the first field studies - within the limits of the researcher's knowledge - that dealt with the relationship between the variables of the study, (2) the study dealt only with the OM variable to those mobbing issued by management and not mobbing issued by colleagues to each other, and (3) the results of the study resulted in a positive and significant correlation between OM and OS. This means that the more nurses feel about OM, the more motivated they are for OS. This result is due to the aggressive behavior of the superiors and the psychological suffering they cause among the nurses, leading them to silence for fear that their ideas and suggestions would be incompatible with their superiors. This leads to further mobbing of them, and this result is consistent with the findings of other studies (Elçi et al., 2014; Gul & Özcan, 2011; Hüsrevşahi, 2015), all of which indicated a positive correlation between OM and OS.

The research concluded that there is a need to: (1) motivate and encourage nurses to give their opinions, ideas and suggestions through granting them financial rewards, (2) hold discussions and meetings between nurses provided that the heads raise a specific problem and then ask each nurse to give his/her opinion in the development of work, (3) notify nurses of their importance, and the importance of their opinions, ideas and suggestions to solve problems and develop working methods, (4) impose penalty when one of the nurses complains about the mistreatment of his boss or his suffering from the mobbing caused to him, (5) build open communication channels between the administration and nurses, so that they can contact the senior management and consult in matters relating to work, (6) work on the importance of behavioral training for administrative leaders in order to develop their behavior to deal positively with nurses, (7) hold concerts and meetings that enhance social relations between all staff, whether doctors, nurses and administrators and supports confidence among them, (8) choose future workers, whether doctors, nurses or administrators in the light of objective criteria related to the job and not according to personal considerations, and (9) ensure respect for nurses in terms of their ideas and opinions and allow them the opportunity to participate in making decisions related to work.

Keywords: Organizational Silence, Organizational Mobbing

1. Introduction

The human element is one of the most important inputs of organizations and even one of the greatest forces influencing their identity and shaping their future. Based on the human element, the efficiency and effectiveness of the organization are determined, and its importance lies in its ability to address organizational problems through innovative solutions (Dankoskic et al., 2014).

Organizational studies and research have shown that despite the possession of the human element, he/she is sometimes reluctant to express his/her opinions, ideas and beliefs, because of firm conviction that the expression of opinions and proposals is somewhat dangerous, which leads to silence about the events and situations experienced by the organization and problems (Eriguc et al., 2014).

When the organization is silent, the frustration of its social networks leaks and its competitive advantages become meaningless, which negatively affects the effectiveness of its organizational decision-

making and leads to the failure of its goals (Karaca, 2013), which hinders change, organizational development and the loss of the ability to correct mistakes. (Zehir & Erdogan, 2011).

O Silence (OS) is due to a number of reasons, including abusive supervision (Kiewitz et al., 2016), and O Mobbing (OM) (Erdirencelebi & Şendogdu, 2016), lack of trust between employees and their supervisors, and OS may arise due to fear of damage to their relationship with their managers (Gul & Özcan, 2011).

OS is the deliberate reluctance on the part of the staff to ask questions or give ideas and information on organizational matters (Brinsfield, 2009), resulting in the organization not hearing the voices of its staff (Deniz et al., 2013).

OS expresses the reluctance of employees to express the results of their emotional, cognitive and behavioral assessment of various organizational situations (Pinder & Harlos, 2001).

There are several implications of OS, as silence is of a significant impact on individuals and the organization (Bogosian, 2012).

OS correlates negatively with three dimensions of organizational trust (trust in the organization, trust in leadership, trust in the supervisor). This means that the more silence means less trust (Nikolaou, et al., 2011).

OS does have implications and consequences on the climate of trust within the organization, because it leads to poor relations of trust between employees due to lack of dialogue between them (Willman et al., 2006).

The effects of OS are not limited to the organization, as it can negatively affect the behavior of individuals working in the organization. These effects are represented in (1) the individual feeling unappreciated, as he does not contribute in earnest in the issues of the organization, reducing the importance and value of his presence, (2) lack of the individual's ability to control, reducing motivations at work and participation in the issues within the organization, and (3) the individual suffering from cognitive dissonance. This is because silence makes it difficult for the individual to strike a balance between his beliefs and behaviors (Hazen, 2006).

There are negative impacts on OS. They are (1) poor participation of employees in decision-making because of the lack of the channels or opportunities of communication, (2) reducing dealing with conflict or dispute in an effective manner, and (3) weakness of the employees' capacity to learning and self-development (Low et al., 2002).

2. Literature Review

2.1. Organizational Mobbing

The historical roots of Mobbing go back to the Latin word "Mobile Vulgus," which refers to groups that tend to be violent, and the act of mob expresses many meanings, including crowd, attack and inconvenience. The concept of mobbing was first used in 1960 by Australian scientist Kandard Lorenz to express riot behavior among animals (Erdoğan, 2009).

It was also used later by the Swedish scientist Parter Paul Heinmann to express violence directed at strong students to fellow physically weak colleagues (Davenport, et al., 2003).

In late 1980, the concept of mobbing was first used in the workplace by psychologists. Leymann was one of the first researchers to treat the concept of OM as an urgent organizational issue. He stressed that organizations also suffer from negative behaviors and that these behaviors may come from an employee within the organization, whether intended or not intended. Such behaviors can be described as disturbing, which entails many organizational problems, and thus lead to a reduction in the level of work performance (Einarsen et al., 1999; Smith et al., 2003).

Bullying involves physical abuse, violence and threats, and the incidence of abuse and physical violence must be very limited in organizations, The term naughty was used to express negative behaviors in schools, and mobbing was used to express negative behaviors in the workplace (Leymann, 1990; 1996).

OM refers to all kinds of hostile attitudes that have many negative outcomes, which can reach the extent of stopping the victim from work and suffering from mental and physical disorders. (Zapf et al., 1996).

OM behaviors take many forms, most notably Leymann (1996):

1. Prevent the individual from expressing his opinion without communicating with him, interrupting him to speak, rebuking him loudly and criticizing him constantly.
2. Abuse of social relations, such as preventing the individual from communicating with others, disrespecting his rights, or claiming his absence from work and his absence.
3. Insulting the employee's reputation and targeting him with unfounded rumors, which has many negative effects.
4. Abusing the individual's professional status, robbing him of his decent job, and assigning him to work that lacks the meaning and importance of the work he does.
5. Working to hinder his success and assigning him to work less than his abilities and skills, and may include changing his job or restricting his duties.
6. Assigning the individual difficult tasks and tasks that exceed his abilities and skills, which reflects negatively on the individual's mental and physical health.
7. Offending the dignity of the individual, cynicism and ridicule of his religious and political beliefs, and to assassinate him in a way that is not in it, and to call him titles and qualities that offend him.

2.2. Organizational Silence

OS occurs when employees intentionally withhold their knowledge and ideas regarding organizational issues. Many organizations have been involved in solving a major puzzle and that is most people know the fact about certain problems of organization but do not have the courage to express those facts to their supervisors (Tulubas & Celep, 2012).

OS is a reflection of many dimensions and variables within business organizations, including the reluctance of staff to submit their views and suggestions for the development of the organization, in addition to lack of interaction with the important work issues of the organization (Bogosian, 2012).

OS is an inefficient organizational process that wastes cost and efforts and can take various forms, such as collection silence in meetings, low levels of participation in suggestion schemes, and low levels of collective voice (Shojaie et al., 2011).

OS can be beneficial in some cases, these are: decrease of administrative information overload, reducing interpersonal conflicts and storage of secret information. Despite these, OS is rather regarded as a harmful phenomenon for both the employee and the organization (Tikici et al., 2011).

OS can negatively affect the harvesting of institutional knowledge, evolution, and development. The possibility of being excluding when speaking up may cause employees to stop communicating and giving feedback to their supervisors. Combined with a failure to support intellectually, employees will lead to ineffective organizational decisions (Kahveci, 2010).

OS is considered as a threat against Organizational Change (OC). It is underlined that many employees do not communicate with their superiors about several issues despite their awareness and it is an obvious contradiction that many organizations experience. OS, which can be defined as withholding opinions and concerns on organizational issues, is a significant topic to be researched (Çakıcı, 2010).

OS is a variable that can prevail about barriers to effectiveness, commitment and performance (Beer 2009).

OS is a phenomenon that requires knowledge of the researches on "voice and silence in organizations." Three periods of research on sound and silence will be reviewed. First period (from the 1970s until 1980s middle): In this decade, the main focus of researches was on the concept of sound. Second period (from 1980s middle until 2000): The main focus of researches was on "Speaking Up." However, little attention was paid to the silencing behaviour during this decade. Current period (from 2000 to now) in which the main focus is on the silence concept (Greenberg & Edwards, 2009).

OS is a phenomenon in business organizations of all types and sizes. It means that employees tend to be silent about the important issues in the organization (Slade, 2008).

OS refers to the collective-level phenomenon of doing or saying very little in response to significant problems or issues facing an organization or industry because of negative reactions (Henriksen & Dayton, 2006).

OS refers to the employee's failure to participate in views and suggestions on important labor issues and choosing to remain silent. OS may cause labour turnover, lack of motivations and a tendency towards

low endeavor for reaching organizational aims. OS may cause insignificance feeling, lack of control perception and cognitive inconsistency (Vakola & Bouradas, 2005).

OS is the common choice made by organization members despite all research extolling the virtues of upward information for organizational health (Rodriguez 2004).

OS is the deliberate prevention of information and opinions by the staff of the organization (Van Dyne, et al., 2003).

OS is a reflection of the forces affecting the relationships between individuals and groups and regulations governing these relationships which prevent staff from talking about the organization's problems (Avan et al., 2003).

OS means the presence of a common perception among employees, limiting their participation in providing their knowledge about the issues and policies of the Organization (Nennete, 2002).

OS is a condition that occurs when people cannot contribute freely to organizational discourse (Bowen & Blackmon, 2003).

OS means that the employee withholds his opinions and suggestions about the work of the organization's problems (Pinder & Harlos, 2001).

OS is interpreted as a collective phenomenon that is a potentially dangerous hindrance to OC and development and also as a significant obstacle to the development of a pluralistic organization (Morrison & Milliken, 2000).

There are two important differentiating characteristics of the OS. First, OS is focused on collective-level dynamics. Second, OS was on why employees intentionally choose to remain silent, rather than on why they do not choose to speak up. OS is the hard choice made by employees within some organizations to keep their thoughts and opinions quiet and shut themselves away from company decisions. OS can lead to several consequences on organizations and employees. Employees believe that they are to be punished openly or discreetly when they express their opinions about organizational issues and faults (Morrison & Milliken, 2000).

OS not only slows down organizational development but also causes several consequences such as decreasing in employees' commitment levels, causing interior conflicts, reducing decision making process, blocking change and innovation, preventing positive or negative feedbacks to the management. OS also causes an increase of behaviours such as breaking down morale and motivations of employees, absenteeism, tardiness and releases which negatively affect individual and organizational activities. Employees who are concerned and under stress, are increasingly involved in the swirl of silence (Morrison & Milliken, 2000).

There are multiple views about the factors leading to OS (Schechtman, 2008), because of its many different determinants or causes, as follows: (1) support the top management of silence, (2) lack of communication opportunities, (3) support of supervisor for silence, (4) official authority, and (5) the subordinate's fear of negative reactions (Brinsfield, 2009).

1. Support of the Top Management of Silence

The role of top management is instrumental in the success of the business organizations. The availability of a high degree of confidence in the administration reduces concerns of speaking freely about the problems of labor. The climate of confidence in the top management reduces the feelings of uncertainty (Weber & Weber, 2001).

The attitudes and values of the top management may contribute greatly to the formation of a climate of silence, as some organizations prohibit employees from saying what they know or feel (Argyris, 1997).

The top management practices may lead to increased levels of silence within the organization. These practices are represented in two factors (Morrission & Milliken, 2000). They are (1) the top management may be afraid of getting negative feedback information from the subordinates, as it may feel threatened as a result of this information, particularly if they involve its members personally or their work. Because of that, those members would eschew this information, and even if it reached them they would neglect it or question the credibility of the source, believing that the feedback from the bottom may be less accurate and less legitimate (Vakola & Bouradas, 2005), and (2) silence increases when the top management is in an ivory tower prohibiting it from seeing the actual reality because of lack of access to information, or due to welcoming the good information rather than the negative (Van, Dyne, et al., 2003). Thus, the support of top

management of silence leads employees not to talk about work issues. Besides, the administration may describe employees who talk about labor issues as problem makers (Milliken, et al., 2003).

2. Lack of Communication Opportunities

Contact is essential to the effectiveness of any organization. It represents the transfer of information verbally or using other means for the purpose of persuasion and influencing the behavior of others. Among the most important functions of the communication process is that it provides individuals with the necessary information for the purpose of decision-making, as it represents an outlet to express feelings, opinions and trends. It is an important means to satisfy the social needs of individuals (Robbins & Judge, 2013).

The more contact opportunities within the organization, the greater participation and expression of opinion on issues and problems of the work, as employees have the opportunity to make suggestions, which increase the degree of career belonging and involvement of employees (Smidts, et al., 2001).

3. Support of Supervisor for Silence

The relationship of supervisor's strength and stature to silence or talking can be analyzed in two ways: on the one hand, the subordinate may tend to talk more than keep silent with a strong supervisor, because this subordinate believes that the supervisor has the ability to resolve any problem or issue related to work. Here, a subordinate finds it useful to talk in the presence of a supervisor who has the power to solve work problems within the organization (Morrison & Milliken, 2000).

On the other hand, the freedom to express dissenting opinion may be restricted when working under the leadership of a supervisor with prestige and power, because the subordinate tends to the option of silence due to fear of the negative impact of expressing the dissent opinion (Turner & Pratkanis, 1998).

The supervisor's behavior creates a microcosm climate of silence at the level of the department where he/she works. Therefore, subordinates tend to silence (Sugarman, 2001).

The subordinates' silence is influenced by trends and tendencies of the supervisors to silence rather than trends and tendencies of top management. Therefore, when the supervisor listens to his subordinates, they will consider him a role model, and tend to involve themselves in labor issues and talk about it (Sparrowe & Liden, 2005).

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In spite of that, the power and status of the supervisor can increase or decrease the silence of subordinates, but many researchers assert that subordinates are more sensitive to the risks of talking more than the benefits, in the presence of a strong supervisor (Edmondson, 1996).

4. Official Authority

Officialdom is the degree by which the activities carried out by employees are formed within the organization, through the adoption of several measures (Moorhead & Criffin, 2004).

Officialdom is based on the strength of the position or location in the organizational structure. Dealing follows specific orders and a bureaucrat approach through decision-making centralization, and the use of regulations to deal with the problems and issues of work. At this point, the organization lacks an effective mechanism for information feedback. This is because there are few upwards communication channels because heads believe that the views of the subordinates are unimportant and therefore tend to silence (Ashford et al., 1998).

5. Subordinate's Fear of Negative Reactions

The fear of the reaction may lead employees to believe that talking about work problems might deprive them of their jobs or upgrade to higher positions within the organization (Milliken, et al., 2003).

3. Research Model

The proposed comprehensive conceptual model is presented in Figure (1). The diagram below shows that there is one independent variable for the study of OM. There is one dependent variable OS.

Figure (1)

Proposed Comprehensive Conceptual Model

The research framework suggests that OM has an impact on the OS of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt. The present study handles OM as an independent variable. The researcher has employed the measure developed by Pranjic et al., 2006, to measure OM. It is worthy of mentioning that this measure consists of 17 statements.

OS, as measured, consisted of support of the top management of silence, lack of communication opportunities, support of supervisor for silence, official authority, and subordinate's fear of negative reactions. This measure consists of 27 statements (Schechtman, 2008; Brinsfield, 2009).

4. Research Questions

The research problem has two sources; first, previous studies, and it turns out that there is a lack in the number of literature review that dealt with the analysis of the relationship between OM and OS of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt. This called for the researcher to test this relationship in the Egyptian environment.

OM is a series of repeated psychological abuse directed at specific individuals, when OM occurs, conflicts and disputes arise, workers' sense of belonging is reduced and their willingness to endure hardships leads them to seek other organizations that allow them to have better working conditions (Tetik, 2010). If these workers remain in the organization, they increase their motivation for OS, because OS is one of the possible reactions of workers subjected to OM (Tas et al., 2013).

One study indicated that OM had a significant effect on increasing its motivation for OS (Erdirencelebi & Şendogdu, 2016).

Another study showed that there is a positive and significant correlation between OM behaviors and OS (Hüsrevşahi, 2015).

Another study aimed to examine the effect of OM on organizational cynicism and found that the feeling of OM significantly affects organizational cynicism (Pelit & Pelit, 2014).

The study examined the relationship between OM, job burnout, and job satisfaction. The results of the study indicated that OM is positively associated with job burnout and negatively with job satisfaction (Civildag, 2014).

Another study focused on addressing the variables of OS and mobbing on the intention to quit work and found that there was a positive and significant effect of both OS and OM on the intention to quit work (Elçi et al., 2014).

Another study aimed to examine the relationship between OM and OS. The results of the study indicated that there is a positive and significant correlation between OM behaviors and OS (Hüsrevşahi, 2015).

The second source is the pilot study, which was conducted an interview with (30) nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt to identify OM and OS. The researcher found through the pilot study several indicators notably the blurred important and vital role that could be played by OM in affecting the OS of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt. The research questions of this study are as follows:

- Q1: What is the nature and extent of the relationship between OM and OS (Support of the Top Management of Silence) of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt?
 Q2: What is the extent of the relationship between OM and OS (Lack of Communication Opportunities) of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt?
 Q3: What is the nature of the relationship between OM and OS (Support of Supervisor for Silence) of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt?
 Q4: What is the extent of the relationship between OM and OS (Official Authority) of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt?
 Q5: What is the relationship between OM and OS (Subordinate's Fear of Negative Reactions) of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt?

5. Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were developed to decide if there is a significant correlation between OM and OS.

- H1: There is no relationship between OM and OS (Support of the Top Management of Silence) of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt.
 H2: OM has no statistically significant effect on OS (Lack of Communication Opportunities) of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt.
 H3: There is no relationship between OM and OS (Support of Supervisor for Silence) of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt.
 H4: There is no relationship between OM and OS (Official Authority) of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt.
 H5: There is no relationship between OM and OS (Subordinate's Fear of Negative Reactions) of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt.

6. Research Population and Sample

The population of the study included only nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt. The total population is 3000 nurses. Determination of respondent sample size was calculated using the formula (Daniel, 1999) as follows:

$$n = \frac{N \times (Z)^2 \times P(1-P)}{d^2 (N-1) + (Z)^2 \times P(1-P)}$$

So the number of samples obtained by 343 nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt is as presented in Table (1).

Table (1) Distribution of the Sample Size

Teaching Hospitals	Nurses	Percentage	Sample Size
Shebin El Koum	784	24%	343X 24% = 82
Damanhour	445	14%	343X 14% = 48
Benha	489	15%	343X 15% = 51
Ahmed Maher	448	14%	343X 14% = 48
Galaa	412	13%	343X 13% = 45
Al Mataria	300	9%	343X 9% = 31
Al Sahel	358	11%	343X 11% = 38
Total	3245	100%	343X 100% = 343

The annual Statistics for the Information Center of the Public Agency for Teaching Hospitals, 2018

Descriptive statistics are used to describe some of the features of the respondents at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt who participated in the survey.

Table (2) provides more detailed information about the sample and the measures.

Table (2) Characteristics of Items of the Sample

Variables		Frequency	Percentage
1- Sex	Male	125	42%
	Female	175	58%
	Total	300	100%
2- Marital Status	Single	85	28%
	Married	215	72%
	Total	300	100%
3- Age	Under 30	125	42%
	From 30 to 45	145	48%
	Above 45	30	10%
	Total	300	100%
4- Educational Level	Secondary school	145	48%
	University	155	52%
	Total	300	100%
5- Period of Experience	Less than 5 years	60	20%
	From 5 to 10	215	72%
	More than 10	25	8%
	Total	300	100%

7. Data Collection

The researcher has used the questionnaire for collecting data. The questionnaire is interested in OM and OS of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt.

The survey included three questions. The first is related to OM, the second detects OS; the third relates to the demographic variables of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt. About 340 questionnaires were distributed. 300 usable questionnaires. The response rate was 88%.

The research depends on the Likert scale for each statement ranging from (5) “full agreement,” (4) for “agree,” (3) for “neutral,” (2) for “disagree,” and (1) for “full disagreement.”

8. Research Variables and Methods of Measuring

The 17-item scale OM of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt is based on Pranjić et al., 2006.

Also, The 27-item scale OS section is based on Schechtman, 2008; and Brinsfield, 2009. There were five items measuring support of the top management of silence, six items measuring lack of communication opportunities, five items measuring support of supervisor for silence, five items measuring official authority, and six items measuring subordinate's fear of negative reactions. The survey form is used as the main tool for data collection in measuring the OS of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt.

Responses to all items scales were anchored on a five (5) point Likert scale for each statement which ranges from (5) “full agreement,” (4) for “agree,” (3) for “neutral,” (2) for “disagree,” and (1) for “full disagreement”.

9. Data Analysis and Hypotheses Testing

9.1. Coding of Variables

The main variables, sub-variables, and methods of measuring variables can be explained in the following table:

Table (3): Description and Measuring of the Research Variables

Main Variables			Number of Statement	Methods of Measuring Variables
Independent Variable	OM	Organizational Mobbing	17	Pranjic et al., 2006
		Total OM	17	
Dependent Variable	OS	Support the top Management of Silence	5	Schechtman, 2008; Brinsfield, 2009
		Lack of Communication Opportunities	6	
		Support Supervisor for Silence	5	
		Official Authority	5	
		Subordinate Fear of Negative Reactions	6	
		Total OS	27	

9.2. Descriptive Analysis

Table (4): shows the mean and standard deviations of OM and OS

Research Variables	Research Variables	Mean	Standard Deviation
OM	OM	3.22	0.653
	Total OM	3.22	0.653
OS	Support the top Management of Silence	3.36	0.942
	Lack of Communication Opportunities	3.47	0.880
	Support Supervisor for Silence	3.40	0.875
	Official Authority	3.49	0.820
	Subordinate Fear of Negative Reactions	3.35	0.846
	Total OS	3.41	0.859

Source: SPSS, V.23, 2015

According to Table (4), among the various facets of OM, most of the respondents identified the total of OM ($M=3.22$, $SD=0.653$).

The second issue examined was the different facets of OS. Most of the respondents identified the total OS ($M=3.41$, $SD=0.859$).

9.3. Evaluating Reliability

Data analysis was conducted. All scales were first subjected to reliability analysis. ACC was used to assess the reliability of the scales. Item analysis indicated that dropping any item from the scales would not significantly raise the alphas.

Table (5): Reliability of OM and OS

Research Variables	Research Variables	Number of Statement	ACC
OM	OM	17	0.937
	Total OM	17	0.937
OS	Support the top Management of Silence	5	0.952
	Lack of Communication Opportunities	6	0.937
	Support Supervisor for Silence	5	0.902
	Official Authority	5	0.879
	Subordinate Fear of Negative Reactions	6	0.901
	Total OS	27	0.984

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of SPSS, V.23, 2015

To assess the reliability of the data, ACC was conducted. Table (5) shows the reliability results for OM and OS.

The 17 items of OM are reliable because ACC is 0.937. Thus, the internal consistency of OM can be acceptable. Also, the 27 items of OS are reliable because ACC is 0.984. Thus, the internal consistency of OS can be acceptable.

9.4. The Means, St. Deviations and Correlation among Variables

Table (6): Means, Standard Deviations and Intercorrelations among Variables

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	OM	OS
Organizational Mobbing	3.22	0.653	1	
Organizational Silence	3.41	0.859	0.073*	1

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of SPSS, V.23, 2015

Table (6) shows correlation coefficients between the research variables, and results indicate the presence of a significant correlation between variables (OM and OS). The level of OM is high (Mean=3.22; SD=0.653), while OS is (Mean=3.41; SD=0.859).

9.5. The Correlation between OM and OS

The relationship between OM and OS of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt is presented in the following table:

Table (7): Correlation Matrix between OM and OS

Research Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6
Organizational Mobbing	1					
Support the top Management of Silence	0.081**	1				
Lack of Communication Opportunities	0.099**	0.971**	1			
Support Supervisor for Silence	0.073**	0.966**	0.944**	1		
Official Authority	0.045**	0.977**	0.958**	0.965**	1	
Subordinate Fear of Negative Reactions	0.056**	0.973**	0.973**	0.940**	0.947**	1

Note: ** Correlation is significant at 0.01 level

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of SPSS, V.23, 2015

Based on the Table (7), the correlation between OM and OS (support the top management of silence) of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt, is 0.056.

For OM and OS (lack of communication opportunities) of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt, the value is 0.973 whereas OM and OS (support supervisor for silence) show a correlation value of 0.973.

Also, the correlation between OM and OS (official authority) of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt is 0.940. For OM and OS (subordinate fear of negative reactions), the value is 0.947. The overall correlation between OM and OS of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt is 0.073.

9.5.1. Organizational Mobbing and OS (Support the top Management of Silence)

The relationship between OM and OS (Support the top Management of Silence) of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt is determined. The first hypothesis to be tested is:

H1: There is no relationship between OM and OS (Support of the Top Management of Silence) of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt.

Table (8) MRA Results for OM and OS (Support of the Top Management of Silence)

The Variables of OM	Beta	R	R ²
1. My boss directs mobbing and obscenity to me.	0.090	0.271	0.073
2. My boss views integrity and integrity as shameful qualities.	0.082	0.276	0.076
3. My boss obscures important information for me.	0.016	0.288	0.082
4. My boss always ignores me in front of others.	0.104	0.269	0.072
5. It is difficult to consult top management on the thorny issues related to my work.	0.529**	0.280	0.078
6. My ideas and opinions are attributed to others in the hospital.	0.381	0.275	0.075
7. My boss directs verbal and behavioral threats.	0.028	0.344	0.118
8. My boss treats me inappropriately in front of others.	0.929**	0.893	0.797
9. I have been subjected to a lot of illegal pressure while doing my job.	0.004	0.485	0.235
10. My boss prevents the thorny issues facing me to top management without consulting me.	0.038	0.008	0.001
11. My boss uses his powers and powers to make threats to me.	0.009	0.056	0.003
12. The tasks I am assigned is exceeded my level of abilities and skills.	0.010	0.029	0.001
13. My boss describes me as not in.	0.009	0.009	0.001
14. Top management does not offer me the motivational techniques to improve my career.	0.000	0.001	0.001
15. The distribution of wages and bonuses is based on the amount of effort.	0.046	0.025	0.001
16. My boss always downplays me in front of others.	0.012	0.027	0.001
17. My boss directs personal abuse while dealing with him.	0.035	0.014	0.001
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.898 0.806 68.994 17, 282 2.03 0.000	

** P < .01

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of SPSS, V.23, 2015

As Table (8) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.898, demonstrating that the 17 independent variables of OM of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt construe OS significantly.

The 17 independent variables of OM of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt can explain 81% of the total factors in OS level. Hence, 19% is explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

9.5.2. Organizational Mobbing and OS (Lack of Communication Opportunities)

The relationship between OM and OS (Lack of Communication Opportunities) of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt is determined. The second hypothesis to be tested is:

H2: There is no relationship between OM and OS (Lack of Communication Opportunities) of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt.

Table (9) MRA Results for OM and OS (Lack of Communication Opportunities)

The Variables of OM	Beta	R	R ²
1. My boss directs mobbing and obscenity to me.	0.046	0.247	0.061
2. My boss views integrity and integrity as shameful qualities.	0.036	0.227	0.051
3. My boss obscures important information for me.	0.051	0.255	0.065
4. My boss always ignores me in front of others.	0.153	0.242	0.058
5. It is difficult to consult top management on the thorny issues related to my work.	0.356	0.254	0.064
6. My ideas and opinions are attributed to others in the hospital.	0.159	0.243	0.059
7. My boss directs verbal and behavioral threats.	0.034	0.341	0.116
8. My boss treats me inappropriately in front of others.	0.953**	0.901	0.811
9. I have been subjected to a lot of illegal pressure while doing my job.	0.015	0.484	0.234
10. My boss prevents the thorny issues facing me to top management without consulting me.	0.185**	0.111	0.012
11. My boss uses his powers and powers to make threats to me.	0.003	0.129	0.016
12. The tasks I am assigned is exceeded my level of abilities and skills.	0.013	0.122	0.014
13. My boss describes me as not in.	0.001	0.084	0.002
14. Top management does not offer me the motivational techniques to improve my career.	0.010	0.002	0.001
15. The distribution of wages and bonuses is based on the amount of effort.	0.046	0.012	0.001
16. My boss always downplays me in front of others.	0.006	0.098	0.001
17. My boss directs personal abuse while dealing with him.	0.137**	0.034	0.001
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.920 0.847 91.719 17, 282 2.03 0.000	

** P < .01

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of SPSS, V.23, 2015

As Table (9) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.920 demonstrating that the 17 independent variables of OM construe OS significantly. The 17 independent variables of OM can explain 84% of the total factors at the OS level. Hence, 16% is explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

9.5.3. Organizational Mobbing and OS (Support Supervisor for Silence)

The relationship between OM and OS (Support Supervisor for Silence) of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt is determined. The third hypothesis to be tested is:

H3: There is no relationship between OM and OS (Support Supervisor for Silence) of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt.**Table (10) MRA Results for OM and OS (Support Supervisor for Silence)**

The Variables of OM	Beta	R	R ²
1. My boss directs mobbing and obscenity to me.	0.144	0.242	0.058
2. My boss views integrity and integrity as shameful qualities.	0.171	0.270	0.072
3. My boss obscures important information for me.	0.003	0.281	0.078
4. My boss always ignores me in front of others.	0.253	0.269	0.072
5. It is difficult to consult top management on the thorny issues related to my work.	0.642	0.268	0.071
6. My ideas and opinions are attributed to others in the hospital.	0.338	0.262	0.068
7. My boss directs verbal and behavioral threats.	0.000	0.455	0.207
8. My boss treats me inappropriately in front of others.	0.801	0.898	0.806
9. I have been subjected to a lot of illegal pressure while doing my job.	0.214	0.652	0.425
10. My boss prevents the thorny issues facing me to top management without consulting me.	0.087	0.049	0.001
11. My boss uses his powers and powers to make threats to me.	0.009	0.092	0.008
12. The tasks I am assigned is exceeded my level of abilities and skills.	0.009	0.070	0.004
13. My boss describes me as not in.	0.002	0.033	0.009
14. Top management does not offer me the motivational techniques to improve my career.	0.003	0.013	0.001
15. The distribution of wages and bonuses is based on the amount of effort.	0.041	0.046	0.001
16. My boss always downplays me in front of others.	0.010	0.050	0.001
17. My boss directs personal abuse while dealing with him.	0.060	0.003	0.001
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.928 0.861 103.182 17, 282 2.03 0.000	
** P < .01			

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of SPSS, V.23, 2015

As Table (10) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.928 demonstrating that the 17 independent variables of OM construe OS significantly. The 17 independent variables of OM can explain 86% of the total factors in OS. Hence, 14% is explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

9.5.4. Organizational Mobbing and OS (Official Authority)

The relationship between OM and OS (Official Authority) of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt is determined. The fourth hypothesis to be tested is:

H4: There is no relationship between OM and OS (Official Authority) of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt.**Table (11) MRA Results for OM and OS (Official Authority)**

The Variables of OM	Beta	R	R ²
1. My boss directs mobbing and obscenity to me.	0.065	0.241	0.058
2. My boss views integrity and integrity as shameful qualities.	0.041	0.240	0.057
3. My boss obscures important information for me.	0.033	0.257	0.066
4. My boss always ignores me in front of others.	0.054	0.243	0.059
5. It is difficult to consult top management on the thorny issues related to my work.	0.323	0.255	0.065
6. My ideas and opinions are attributed to others in the hospital.	0.221	0.246	0.060
7. My direct boss directs verbal and behavioral threats.	0.177**	0.515	0.265
8. My boss treats me inappropriately in front of others.	0.854**	0.900	0.810
9. I have been subjected to a lot of illegal pressure while doing my job.	0.011	0.566	0.320
10. My boss prevents the thorny issues facing me to top management without consulting me.	0.044	0.015	0.001
11. My boss uses his powers and powers to make threats to me.	0.004	0.071	0.005
12. The tasks I am assigned is exceeded my level of abilities and skills.	0.008	0.038	0.001
13. My boss describes me as not in.	0.009	0.013	0.001
14. Top management does not offer me the motivational techniques to improve my career.	0.004	0.004	0.001
15. The distribution of wages and bonuses is based on the amount of effort.	0.052	0.036	0.001
16. My boss always downplays me in front of others.	0.003	0.040	0.001
17. My boss directs personal abuse while dealing with him.	0.041	0.007	0.001
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.919 0.844 89.779 17, 282 2.03 0.000	

** P < .01

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of SPSS, V.23, 2015

As Table (11) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.919, demonstrating that the 17 independent variables of OM construe OS significantly.

The 17 independent variables of OM can explain 84% of the total factors at the OS level. Hence, 16% is explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

9.5.5. Organizational Mobbing and OS (Subordinate Fear of Negative Reactions)

The relationship between OM and OS (Subordinate Fear of Negative Reactions) of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt is determined. The fifth hypothesis is:

H5: There is no relationship between OM and OS (Subordinate Fear of Negative Reactions) of nurses at Teaching Hospitals in Egypt.**Table (12) MRA Results for OM and OS (Subordinate Fear of Negative Reactions)**

The Variables of OM	Beta	R	R ²
1. My boss directs mobbing and obscenity to me.	0.051	0.227	0.051
2. My boss views integrity and integrity as shameful qualities.	0.033	0.223	0.049
3. My boss obscures important information for me.	0.038	0.244	0.059
4. My direct boss always ignores me in front of others.	0.327**	0.231	0.053
5. It is difficult to consult top management on the thorny issues related to my work.	0.468	0.230	0.052
6. My ideas and opinions are attributed to others in the hospital.	0.100	0.221	0.048
7. My boss directs verbal and behavioral threats.	0.057	0.317	0.100
8. My boss treats me inappropriately in front of others.	0.928**	0.861	0.741
9. I have been subjected to a lot of illegal pressure while doing my job.	0.010	0.459	0.210
10. My boss prevents the thorny issues facing me to top management without consulting me.	0.048	0.011	0.001
11. My boss uses his powers and powers to make threats to me.	0.005	0.061	0.001
12. The tasks I am assigned is exceeded my level of abilities and skills.	0.000	0.035	0.001
13. My boss describes me as not in.	0.013	0.009	0.001
14. Top management does not offer me the motivational techniques to improve my career.	0.002	0.010	0.001
15. The distribution of wages and bonuses is based on the amount of effort.	0.072	0.040	0.001
16. My boss always downplays me in front of others.	0.003	0.034	0.001
17. My boss directs personal abuse while dealing with him.	0.049	0.023	0.001
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.872 0.761 52.685 17, 282 2.03 0.000	

** P < .01

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of SPSS, V.23, 2015

As Table (12) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.872 demonstrating that the independent variables of OM construe OS significantly. The 17 independent variables of OM can explain 76% of the total factors at the OS level. Hence, 24% is explained by other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

10. Research Results

By reviewing the results of the descriptive analysis of the data on which the study was based and testing the research hypothesis, the study reached a set of results which will be reviewed and discussed as follows:

1. Despite the availability of numerous regulatory studies on variables of OM and OS, the researchers did not try to examine the relationship between them. Therefore, the aim of the present study is to bridge this research gap. Therefore, the study focused on analyzing the relationship between OM and OS . Hence, the current study is one of the first field studies - within the limits of the researcher's knowledge - that dealt with the relationship between the variables of the study.
2. The study dealt only with the OM variable to those mobbing issued by management and not mobbing issued by colleagues to each other.
3. The results of the study resulted in a positive and significant correlation between OM and OS . This means that the more nurses feel about OM, the more motivated they are for OS . This result is due to the aggressive behavior of the superiors and the psychological suffering they cause among the nurses, leading them to silence for fear that their ideas and suggestions would be incompatible with their superiors. This leads to further mobbing of them, and this result is consistent with the findings of other studies (Elçi et al., 2014; Gul & Özcan, 2011; Hüsrevşahi, 2015), all of which indicated a positive correlation between OM and OS .

11. Recommendations

In the light of the previous results, the researcher concluded with a set of recommendations as follows:

1. To motivate and encourage nurses to give their opinions, ideas and suggestions through granting them financial rewards.
2. Hold discussions and meetings among nurses provided that the heads raise a specific problem and then ask each nurse to give his opinion in the development of work.
3. Management should notify nurses of their importance and the importance of their opinions, ideas and suggestions to solve problems and develop working methods.
4. When one of the nurses complains about the mistreatment of his boss or his suffering from the mobbing caused to him, his boss must be punished so as not to keep up with his actions.
5. Building open communication channels between the administration and nurses, so that they can contact the senior management and consult in matters relating to work.
6. The need to work on the importance of behavioral training for administrative leaders in order to develop their behavior to deal positively with nurses.
7. Holding concerts and meetings that enhance social relations among all staff, whether doctors, nurses and administrators and supports confidence among them.
8. The need to choose future workers, whether doctors, nurses, or administrators in the light of objective criteria related to the job and not according to personal considerations.
9. Ensuring respect for nurses in terms of their ideas and opinions and allowing them the opportunity to participate in making decisions related to work.

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